

Call for Proposals

Innovative eScience Technologies

(eTEC 2020)

Advancing Academic Research through Innovation in eScience and
Data Science Technologies

2020

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1 Introduction

1.1 Background

The Netherlands eScience Center is the national center of expertise for innovative software solutions in all academic research.

As a result of large-scale digitalization, the academic landscape has undergone far-reaching transformations over the last decade. Computer-assisted research has become software driven: we are able to apply digital methods because we have access, not just to hardware and data, but to highly sophisticated software. New technologies are rapidly evolving, while nationally and internationally, organizations are investing heavily in infrastructure and data management. Researchers are expected to work according to open science principles and the impact of European digital developments on their work is only expected to grow. To a large extent, this shifting environment is a generic challenge, with commonalities across all research disciplines. In recent years, the commonalities in the management and exploitation of research data, and the development of innovative software solutions, spawned a new research strategy referred to as *digitally enhanced science*, or *eScience*.

eScience is a term that arose in the UK around the turn of the century to refer to computationally intensive research, often based on large amounts of data and involving crossovers between research domains. In the Netherlands the term has been used over the last decade to denote *computer-assisted research based on advanced software engineering*. Key aspects of eScience now include software quality, sustainability and reusability. Relevant eScience technologies now range from machine learning, visualization and handling sensor data to linked data, accelerators and high-performance computing. eScience initiatives have been institutionalized as part of universities or research groups in various countries, including the UK, the USA, Sweden and Denmark.

The Netherlands eScience Center

The Netherlands eScience Center is the national center of expertise for innovative software solutions in academic research. Our aim is to bridge the gap between digital technologies on the one hand and scientific and scholarly inquiry on the other. Bringing together knowledge, people and institutions, we build and apply software to enhance the use of digital technology in research. Our vision is to establish a robust research community, in which all investigators in all domains are able to exploit advanced digital technologies to answer curiosity-driven research questions, keeping the Netherlands at the forefront of cutting-edge international research. As a national centre the Netherlands eScience Center is unique in the world.

We share our ideas and the research software we develop. Together with a wide range of partner organizations, we advance not just the research projects we fund and collaborate in, but the state of academic research in general.

We are convinced that research in every academic discipline can be improved by taking advantage of available digital technologies. We take a multidisciplinary approach, using our deep knowledge of both academic research and software development to help define and solve innovative research challenges.

Core Technological Competences

The eScience Center develops, scouts and applies the technologies and software best suited to solving state-of-the-art research questions. The core technological competences of the eScience Center are therefore inherently dynamic yet focused. The eScience Center has identified a series of technologies that underpin existing projects and that will remain crucial in many research directions for the foreseeable future. This allows the eScience Center to serve as an essential partner in a large variety of research projects dealing with data- and compute-intensive problems.

Next to advanced expertise in **software quality** and **software engineering best practices**, the eScience Center's current core technological competences include:

- **Optimized Data Handling**, incl. FAIR data, streaming data, databases, linked data, data fusion;
- **Big Data Analytics**, incl. machine learning, natural language processing, search, computer vision, visualization.
- **Efficient Computing**, incl. high-performance, distributed, and energy-aware computing, efficient algorithms, scalability.

A further description of the eScience Center's core technological competences is provided in Appendix A.

It is the intention for projects funded by the eScience Center to utilize and exploit these core technological competences in pursuit of their scientific goals. However, the eScience Center is also committed to working with project leaders, strategic associates and partner organizations to develop additional expertise, and to adapt to needs, urgencies and external developments.

1.2 Purpose of this call

This call for proposals aims to support research and development of *innovative eScience technologies and software* associated with optimized data handling, data analytics and efficient computing, *driven by a demand from any specified **Research Discipline*** (a scientific or scholarly domain selected by the research team itself).

A competitive proposal aims to deliver prototype eScience instruments (e.g. in the form of compute kernels, software libraries, interfaces, algorithms, methods), and will help establish or strengthen research software infrastructures or scientific workflows, with the aim of enhancing and accelerating breakthroughs in the selected Research Discipline. Each project must focus on one of the '**Technological Research Directions**' described below.

Projects awarded in this call for proposals typically will be led by either:

- a technology-oriented PI from the selected Research Discipline, or
- a domain-oriented PI from ICT Science (i.e. a technical discipline such as data science or computer science). *In this case, it is required to include at least one co-applicant & team member from the selected Research Discipline as well.*

Innovative, reusable eScience technologies

In the context of this call for proposals, innovative eScience technologies are defined as technological (software) advancements that help enable research activities, or open up new research directions, that are not easily pursued using existing methods or tools. The availability of such technologies would impact the daily practice of researchers in the selected Research Discipline and would contribute significantly to the acceleration of the scientific discovery process therein.

First and foremost, a submitted proposal clearly expresses the research challenges underlying the development of such technologies. The need for the technologies will be substantiated by clear and urgent compute- or data-driven research questions from the selected Research Discipline. For *at least one* of these discipline-driven research questions a proof-of-concept must be developed and verified.

On top of this, a competitive proposal will explain to what extent, and in what way, the developed technologies and software will have value to other research problems – within the same research domain, or even in other domains. Next to this potential for reuse and generalization, a competitive proposal provides a sustainability section, describing measures taken to ensure the usability and availability of the developed technologies and software beyond the duration of the project itself.

Technological Research Directions

In this call for proposals, four main Technological Research Directions have been selected for which advances in research and development are timely and urgent. Each application must indicate which of the Technological Research Directions the proposed work applies to (most). For all the Technological Research Directions we require proposals to take reproducibility of experiments, and reusability of software and tools, into account. Proposals are evaluated and ranked within their selected Technological Research Direction. This call aims to fund 1 proposal in each direction.

I. Tools for Data Quality, Integration and Cleaning

With the recent advances of machine learning (ML), especially deep learning, many researchers opt to use the power of these technologies for tackling their scientific challenges. Collecting the large amount of training data takes significant time and effort followed by a process to ensure data quality. This is needed to make the data **AI-ready**. The data must be cleaned, preprocessed and labeled, which is a very expensive and often iterative process. Many researchers report that more than 80% of their time is spent on these tasks before the actual learning phase. Also, before machine learning can succeed for scientific applications, the data must first be well understood. Therefore, it is crucial to develop more **efficient tools for data cleaning, integration and visual inspection**. Enriching the ML models by integrating expert knowledge is also paramount for the success of using ML for research. Related topics also include **visual analytics and anomaly detection**.

II. Virtual Research Environments: Infrastructure for '1000' Experiments

Academic research is increasingly becoming digital, moving from research-in-the-lab to research-in-the-cloud. However, individual researchers often must put in the effort of building their own virtual research environments, as reusable infrastructures for conducting digital research are still in their infancy. We aim to support projects which improve the state-of-the-art of tools and infrastructures for reproducible digital research, in particular covering: tools for **FAIR data, software and workflows**; tools for facilitating **reproducibility** and preserving **provenance** of experiments; and tools for automating **software publishing, citation and metrics**.

III. Platforms for Big & Complex Spatial Data

Many fields of research, ranging from politics to ecology, depend upon geospatial models of our surroundings. Increases in size and complexity of these models make it possible to answer new research questions. We seek research projects that take these developments to the next level. Examples are improvements on tools for **geospatial satellite data**, tools to process **point clouds**, and **parallel spatial algorithms or data structures** (e.g. for Spark, Storm, etcetera).

IV. Green Computing: Energy Efficiency in Research Computing

Currently, research computing can run computations and process data volumes at unprecedented scale. However, the energy requirements of these experiments are also becoming prohibitively large. Often, the costs of running data and compute centers is dominated by the energy bill, not the hardware costs. Optimizing algorithms for energy efficiency instead of just performance will help alleviate this problem, for example by designing **energy efficient algorithms, autotuning** existing algorithms for energy efficiency, or replacing numerical simulations with more **energy efficient machine learning-based surrogate models**.

Open Source/Open Access

This call for proposals specifically targets proposals that aim to develop (standards-based) open source/open access solutions¹, where possible extending or working in concert with the core technological competences of Appendix A and made available as part of the Research Software Directory (Appendix B). For all awarded projects and under supervision of the eScience Center an effort is made to enhance development of sustainable and re-usable software solutions. To this end, additional manpower will be made available on top of the awarded grant itself (Section 1.3).

e-Infrastructure

An additional purpose of this call is to improve and expand the link between state-of-the-art scientific research questions and the capabilities of advanced e-Infrastructure (e.g. high-performance computing, large-scale data storage and management; see also Appendix D). For this reason, specific infrastructural support services may be provided by SURFsara or SURFnet to proposals with clear e-Infrastructure needs.

¹ Applicants are asked to endorse and follow the [NLeSC Strategy towards Publishing, Licensing, and IP](#). For alternative agreements, contact the eScience Center before proposal submission.

Research Consortium

As stated above, typically the project leader either will be working in (and have leading expertise in) the selected Research Discipline, or in ICT Science. Given the nature of many of today's data- and compute-intensive research problems, however, proposals of multidisciplinary teams to achieve their scientific goals are specifically welcomed. Public-private collaborations are positively valued, but the inclusion of industrial partners as part of the research team is not a requirement.

1.3 Available budget

In this call, each grant will consist of two parts: 1) a cash contribution for the employment of local research personnel and other expenses, and 2) in-kind support in the form of highly skilled eScience Research Software Engineers (eScience RSEs, see Section 2.2) employed by the eScience Center.

In this call, the total available budget is as follows: k€1012 in cash funding and 10.0 PYR² in-kind funding. With a total of 4 projects to be awarded, a typical project will receive k€253 and 2.5 PYR contribution in the form of eScience RSEs employed by the eScience Center and whose time is allocated to the project.

On top of this, the eScience Center will contribute 2.8 PYR jointly to the 4 awarded projects, to enhance the development of sustainable and reusable software solutions and to ensure impact beyond the lifetime of the project (and, if possible, beyond the selected Research Discipline). This extra contribution is under supervision of the eScience Center and need not to be included in the project description or budget.

It is the aim of this call to grant 1 project in each of the Technological Research Directions described in Section 1.2.

1.4 Validity of this call

This call for proposals is valid for the assessment procedure of pre-proposals submitted before the deadline of Thursday **25 June 2020, 14:00 CET**, and full proposals submitted before the deadline of Thursday **22 October 2020, 14:00 CET**.

² PYR = Person Years; 1.0 PYR represents 1680 hours available for the duration of the project.

2 Guidelines for applicants

2.1 Who can apply?

Proposals can be submitted by researchers from any Dutch university or research institute affiliated with NWO or KNAW. Each proposal is to be formally submitted by a single named researcher (the 'principal investigator' or PI) on behalf of a team comprising researchers from one or more institutes. The PI is also the proposed project leader. A copy of the proposal must be submitted to the director or dean of the PI's institute. Proposals are granted only if the PI's institute has been informed of the proposal and accepts the conditions relating to grants awarded in this call.

Further requirements:

The PI must:

- have a PhD;
- hold a contract for at least the duration of the requested project or provide a letter of intent signed by the director or dean of the PI's institute indicating that the PI's employment will be guaranteed for at least the duration of the requested project.

Co-authors of the proposal are encouraged to be part of the research team and to serve as co-applicants of the proposal. This also includes researchers (postdocs) for whom funding is being requested.

The PI will be responsible for scientific progress and reporting. Financial accounting is a shared responsibility of the PI and the Netherlands eScience Center.

It is encouraged to have links with business partners to enlarge the potential for valorization of the project. As such, it is possible for co-applicants to be employed by a non-academic partner.

Further conditions:

In addition to the above requirements, the following conditions hold:

- the PI may submit only one proposal in that capacity in this call;
- the PI may not also submit a (pre-)proposal in that capacity in other large calls published by the Netherlands eScience Center in 2020;
- the research team may not submit identical/very similar proposals in this call;
- the PI (and research team) can only submit a full proposal in the second phase of this call if he/she also submitted a pre-proposal in the first phase.

2.2 What can be applied for?

A project grant may be requested for a maximum total in cash budget of **k€253** and a minimum in-kind budget of **2.5 PYR** from the eScience Center. The project duration must be between 30 and 42 months.

eScience Research Software Engineers and eScience Coordinators

The experts who build eScience software are called Research Software Engineers or RSEs. The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) offers the following description of RSEs: *"A growing number of people in academia combine expertise in programming with an intricate understanding of research. Research Software Engineers may start as researchers who spend time developing software to progress their research. They may also come from a more conventional software development background and are drawn to research by the challenge of using software to further research."* To distinguish RSEs working at research institutes from those working at the Netherlands eScience Center, we call the latter **eScience RSEs**.

eScience RSEs will become an integral part of the projected research team. Apart from their specific focus on the development of high-quality research software, they will help to interpret the results of the research and make the delivered eScience tools useable for a broad range of users. Typically, they will also co-author research publications together with the research team. The eScience RSEs perform their project activities both at the eScience Center in Amsterdam and at the project locations (often at the institute of the main applicant).

The **eScience Coordinator** is an experienced project manager, responsible for the daily supervision of the RSE(s) assigned to the project and is – together with the PI – in charge of monitoring progress and the delivery of project results.

The available in cash budget is primarily intended to cover expenses for local research personnel. Part of the cash budget, however, may also be reserved for additional resources and expenditures. Typically (but not exclusively), the project budget will be as follows:

- a. **1 Postdoc position for the duration of 3.0 years.** The cost associated with this position includes an individual bench fee of up to k€5 as a contribution to travelling expenses, or other approved expenditure. Budget for local personnel should follow the most recent VSNU agreement³.
- b. **A maximum of k€15** for project-related equipment and software, and travel expenses by non-eScience Center personnel. Costs for equipment and software must equal or exceed k€5, and its necessity must be justified; equipment and software with a purchase price of less than k€5 is deemed part of the standard infrastructure of the local institute and is therefore ineligible for funding. Travel expenses must be incurred by the project team members, with a maximum of k€10. The necessity of travel, equipment and software in support of the project must be justified.

The total of a) + b) may not exceed k€253.

³ See: <http://www.nwo.nl/financiering/hoer-werkt-dat/salaristabellen>. Note that VSNU agreements typically are renewed every year. Therefore, in the pre-proposal the budget is taken as indicative. In the full proposal phase, the budget must follow the latest VSNU agreement precisely.

- c. **A minimum of 2.5 PYR** in terms of support provided by personnel employed by the eScience Center. Of the total requested PYR, 85% covers all activities performed directly on behalf of the project by one or more eScience Research Software Engineers, and by the assigned eScience Coordinator who oversees the project at the eScience Center. The remaining 15% comprises activities to the benefit of academic research in general (incl. internal communication, knowledge transfer, and training).

In case more than 2.5 PYR is requested, the budget for a) + b) is lowered by k€ 8,5 per 0.1 PYR.

Distribution of the in-kind contribution over the project period will be determined together with the eScience Center at the start of the project.

2.3 When can applications be submitted?

The round consists of two phases:

1. A mandatory pre-proposal phase, in which the main research ideas and projected outcomes are to be outlined. The application form can be obtained from the eScience Center webpage for this call (via www.esciencecenter.nl/collaborate). Closing date for submission of pre-proposals is **25 June 2020, 14:00 CET**.
2. The full proposal phase, in which selected applicants are invited by the independent Assessment Committee to submit a detailed application. A full proposal may be submitted only in case the applicants also submitted a pre-proposal in the first phase. The application form can be obtained from the eScience Center webpage for this call (via www.esciencecenter.nl/collaborate). Closing date for submission of full proposals is **22 October 2020, 14:00 CET**.

Further information about the procedure, including a timetable, is found in Section 3.1.

2.4 Preparing an application

A pre-proposal has three parts: a fact sheet, the application form, and a list of suggested referees / non-referees. A full proposal has two parts: a fact sheet, and the application form.

- The fact sheet can be completed directly in ISAAC, the electronic application system of NWO (www.isaac.nwo.nl). While completing the fact sheet, you can only make use of ASCII symbols ("plain text"). Therefore, use of (structural) formulas, illustrations, italics, etcetera in the fact sheet is not possible. A link to the ISAAC submission system is available on the eScience Center webpage for this call: www.esciencecenter.nl/collaborate.

- The correct application form must be used for preparing the proposal. The form is obtained from the eScience Center webpage for this Call. The completed form must be attached to the ISAAC fact sheet as a PDF file.
- A list of possible referees/non-referees should be added to the ISAAC fact sheet, and explicitly not be included in the proposal text itself. For more information, please refer to Section 2.6.
- Possible letters of intent from (for example) private partners should be added to the ISAAC fact sheet in a separate PDF-file.
- Applications must be completed in English.
- The layout of the proposal should facilitate its readability. Use a font size of at least 10 points.

2.5 Specific conditions

The specific conditions that are valid for granted proposals are as follows:

- In case the proposal has been submitted to more than one competition, it can be awarded only once.
- Awarded projects must commence within six months of the award date. If the project has not started within that period, the Board of the Netherlands eScience Center has the right to withdraw the grant.
- In case any components (such as data sets, specialized hardware, etcetera) necessary for starting or continuing the proposed research are not available either at the start of the project or at the date specified in the project workplan, the eScience Center Board has the right to withdraw the grant.
- In case projected deliverables (i.e. research papers, software tools, data sets, or otherwise) have not been realized at the approximate date specified in the project workplan, the eScience Center Board has the right to withdraw the grant.
- **FAIR:** Researchers funded within this call must use the FAIR principles and recommendations with respect to the sharing of data⁴ and software⁵.

Open Access

All scientific publications resulting from research that is funded by grants derived from this call for proposals are to be immediately (at the time of publication) freely accessible worldwide (Open Access). There are several ways for researchers to publish Open Access. A detailed explanation regarding Open Access can be found on www.nwo.nl/openscience-en.

Data Management / Software Sustainability

Responsible data management and high-quality software are part of good research. The eScience Center expects data and software that emerge from publicly funded research to become freely and sustainably available, as much as possible, for reuse by other researchers. Furthermore, the eScience Center aims to raise awareness among researchers of the importance of responsible data management and software

⁴ The FAIR Data Principles, see <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles>

⁵ The FAIR Software Recommendations, see <https://fair-software.nl>

sustainability, amongst other to enhance correctness and reproducibility of scientific results. Proposals should therefore satisfy the data management and software sustainability protocols of the eScience Center. Both protocols consist of two steps:

1. Data management section / software sustainability section

The data management and software sustainability sections are part of the research proposal. Researchers should answer several questions about data management and software sustainability within their intended research project. Therefore, before the research starts the researcher will be asked to think about how the data collected must be ordered and categorized, and how the research software created will be licensed and published, so that these can be made freely available. Measures will often need to be taken during data and software production to make long-term storage, dissemination and re-use possible, also after the project has finished. Researchers can state which research data and software they consider relevant for storage, publication and reuse.

2. Data management plan / software sustainability plan

After a proposal has been awarded, the researcher should elaborate the data management and software sustainability *sections* into data management and software sustainability *plans*. Both plans should be provided to the eScience Center within a maximum of 4 months after the project has started. The eScience Center will approve the plans as quickly as possible. Approval of the data management and software sustainability plans is a condition for disbursement of the funding. The plans can be adjusted during the research. The eScience Center requests PIs to use one of several *certified data management templates* (see: www.lcrdm.nl), to best match the details of the awarded project and/or any specific requirements of the PI's research institute. Further information on data management and software sustainability are available on the eScience Center website (www.esciencecenter.nl/collaborate).

The NWO Regulation on Granting applies insofar as it does not deviate from the specific conditions in this call for proposals.

2.6 Submitting an application

- A proposal can be submitted only via NWO's electronic application system ISAAC. Applications submitted otherwise will not be admitted to the selection procedure. The PI is obliged to submit the proposal via his/her personal ISAAC account. If the PI does not yet have an ISAAC account, this should be created at least one day before the submission deadline (www.isaac.nwo.nl). Possible registration problems may then still be resolved on time. If the PI already has a personal ISAAC account, the creation of a new account is not needed. For technical questions, please contact the ISAAC helpdesk (see Section 4.1.2).
- The proposal must be submitted as a PDF document and should arrive no later than the deadline set in Section 2.3.
- In the submission process in ISAAC, you will be requested to provide additional information. Please take this into account with regards to the set deadline.
- Applicants are requested to suggest up to three international referees. Please give their full names, email address and web address. You should not propose

anyone with whom you have recently collaborated or with whom you intend to collaborate in the near future, whether as co-authors or in other forms of joint undertaking. Only referees who are not directly involved in the research project and research team to which your application refers can be considered. Moreover, suggested referees must not currently hold an appointment in the Netherlands.

- It is possible (but not mandatory) to give the names of up to three people who should NOT be approached as referee. In the interest of confidentiality, these names should not be included in the application itself but be provided in ISAAC separately (before the deadline set in Section 2.3).
- The proposal summary provided in ISAAC, and the summary for non-experts, may be used for publication purposes, should your application be granted.
- In accordance with the agreement between NWO and the Association of Dutch Universities (VSNU), applicants should inform their employing institute of the submission by sending a copy of the application to the scientific director or dean of the institute or department. It is therefore assumed that the employing institute or university is informed of, and accepts, this call's granting conditions.

3 Assessment procedure

3.1 Procedure

Information event

To further inform interested applicants of the specific aims of this call for proposals, the mission and approach of the eScience Center, the role and expertise of the eScience Research Software Engineers, the software technologies implemented and applied by the eScience Center, and the capabilities of the Dutch National e-Infrastructure, an information event will be organized on **3 June 2020**⁶. Registration is required via www.esciencecenter.nl. Attendance by at least one team member at the event is highly recommended, but not mandatory.

Pre-proposal

The first evaluation of all submitted pre-proposals is carried out by eScience experts and Technology Leads at the eScience Center (see also Figure 1). This evaluation covers only the eScience and technology criteria outlined in Section 3.2 (eScience and technology state-of-the-art, sustainability, re-use potential and lateral impact). In this phase, the scientific quality, novelty and impact is explicitly not evaluated. The results of this evaluation are handed over to the independent Assessment Committee (AC; see Section 4.2) as input for their assessment of the pre-proposals.

Based on the pre-proposals and the results of the above evaluation, and using the criteria outlined in Section 3.2, the Assessment Committee reviews and prioritizes the proposals within each *Technological Research Direction* (see Section 1.2), and advises the eScience Center on the highest ranked proposals that should be worked out into a full proposal.

Approximately eight weeks after the pre-proposal submission deadline, applicants will receive the AC advice, stating whether they are invited to proceed with a full proposal. Based on the AC advice, the eScience Center may suggest that applicants intending to work on closely related subjects submit a joint proposal.

Mid-procedure meeting

Applicants invited to submit a full proposal are also invited for a personal meeting with eScience Center experts. In the meeting, applicants are given advice on how to best incorporate any comments of the Assessment Committee, how to exploit the competences of the eScience Center in full, and how to best cover all review criteria.

Applicants with a negative AC advice are not invited for a mid-procedure meeting. The eScience Center has capacity to provide this support for the invited finalists only.

⁶ Due to the coronavirus outbreak, this may take the form of a video streaming event or another form of online information provisioning. Consult the eScience Center website regularly for the latest information.

eScience Center employees are not allowed to write any part of the proposal, or to serve as co-applicant.

Full proposal

All submitted full proposals are sent to independent international peer-reviewers. In parallel, and if applicable, the eScience Center will request applicants to make available all data sets and software that serve as the starting points for the research and that are necessary for investigating the proposal's research questions. The eScience Center will perform 'software and data health checks' (see Appendix C), to make sure the data and software do not require substantial cleaning or overhaul (that would otherwise interfere with a proper execution of the project, if awarded).

The review reports of the international peer-reviewers, as well as the findings of the eScience Center, are sent to the applicants. Based on these reports, the applicants are given the opportunity to write a rebuttal. In a meeting, the AC will discuss all proposals using the submitted proposal texts, the peer-reviews, the software and data health check reports, and the rebuttals from the applicants. Proposals will be assessed following the criteria explained in Section 3.2.

In case a negative evaluation was given by the eScience Center in the pre-proposal phase, it may give further advice to the Assessment Committee based on the full proposal, again only covering the eScience and technology criteria. In case the second evaluation by the eScience Center is negative as well, the Board of the eScience Center (see below) may ignore a potentially positive AC advice and decide to not grant the proposal. Similarly, in case the result of the software and data health check is negative, the Board of the eScience Center may ignore a positive AC advice and decide to not grant the proposal.

Figure 1. Overview of assessment procedure.

Applications are assessed within the Technological Research Direction selected by the proposers at the time of submission. Based on the prioritization and ranking of applications in each of the Technological Research Directions defined in this call, the AC will compose a recommendation for granting and rejection to the Board of the Netherlands eScience Center. The AC aims to recommend one proposal for funding in each of the Technological Research Directions in this call.

Granting Decision

The Board of the Netherlands eScience Center decides on the awarded grants, based on the recommendations of the Assessment Committee.

Timetable

<i>3 June 2020</i>	Information event
<i>25 June 2020</i>	Deadline pre-proposals
<i>End of August 2020</i>	AC evaluation and prioritization
<i>Early September 2020</i>	Announcement of results of pre-proposal round
<i>22 October 2020</i>	Deadline full proposals
<i>Mid-December 2020</i>	Applicants receive peer-reviews and health check reports, and are given the opportunity to respond
<i>Mid-January 2021</i>	AC evaluation and prioritization
<i>Mid-February 2021</i>	Applicants informed of final decision

3.2 Admissibility and assessment criteria

3.2.1 Formal admissibility of applications

A proposal will be assessed only when all of the following conditions have been met:

- the proposal has been submitted by a researcher at a recognized institution (see Section 2.1);
- the proposal is consistent with the purpose of the call (see Section 1.2);
- the proposal was submitted online via ISAAC;
- the proposal was submitted before the deadline;
- the proposal meets the conditions and requirements of this call for proposals.

Once officially declared admissible, the proposal will be processed. Proposals with serious errors or omissions may be disqualified.

3.2.2 Assessment of contents

Proposals will be assessed by the referees and by the Assessment Committee based on the criteria below:

Scientific quality (25%)

- the proposed research should be at the forefront of the state-of-the-art within the selected Technological Research Direction, also at an international level;
- the research team should be of the highest quality, and – if possible – already be recognized as representative (and authoritative) with respect to the proposed research questions, direction, and long-term vision.

Scientific novelty and impact (25%)

- the proposed research within the selected Technological Research Direction should be novel and – at the same time – support the longer term aim of solving a specific, major challenge in the selected Research Discipline;
- the proposed research should potentially change the modus operandi of research practice within the selected Research Discipline, in terms of broadness, scale, speed of result-delivery, or otherwise;
- the proposed research can be expected to lead to one or more significant results (either directly within the selected Technological Research Direction, or indirectly in terms of a significant advancement within the selected Research Discipline);
- the proposal must indicate which efforts are made to promote the results of the project (publications, demonstrations, workshops, training, etcetera).

eScience and technology state-of-the-art (25%)

- the eScience and data science technologies (e.g. software for data analytics, data management, efficient computing, etcetera) researched and developed should be state-of-the-art and appropriate, meaning that no alternative (proven) technologies exist that would better serve the needs or demands of the selected Research Discipline, or lead to more significant scientific breakthroughs;
- the research team should show awareness of the state-of-the-art of alternative (relevant) technologies; PIs can first contact the eScience Center, if needed.

Lateral impact, re-use and sustainability (25%)

- the proposal must indicate how the developed solutions will find use beyond the proposed work itself, preferably across disciplines, also after finalization of the project;
- the developed solutions and (software) deliverables must be open source/open access and permit use and/or interpretation by other researchers;
- the proposal must indicate how the project will build further collaborations, in academic research, industry, or both; inclusion of concrete letters of intent from such foreseen partners will be valued positively, but is not required;
- the proposal must indicate how long-term maintenance and sustainability of project results (in particular software and data) will be secured and managed.

4 Contact details

4.1 Contact

4.1.1 Specific questions about this call

If you have specific questions about this call for proposals and the assessment procedure, please contact:

Tom van Rens MSc, Program Officer NWO

Tel.: +31 (0)70 344 0509

Email: e-science@nwo.nl

For questions about the Netherlands eScience Center, or the eScience requirements for this call, please contact:

Dr. Frank J. Seinstra, Program Director Netherlands eScience Center

Tel.: +31 (0)20 460 4770

Email: open-calls@esciencecenter.nl

4.1.2 Technical questions about the electronic application system ISAAC

For technical questions about the use of ISAAC, please contact the ISAAC helpdesk. Applicants are requested to read the ISAAC manual before consulting the helpdesk.

The ISAAC helpdesk is available from Monday to Friday from 10.00 to 17.00 hours on +31 (0)20 346 7179. You can also send your questions to isaac.helpdesk@nwo.nl. You will receive a reply within two working days.

4.2 Other information

4.2.1 Members of the Assessment Committee

A separate Assessment Committee (AC) will be set up for the evaluation of the proposals submitted in this call. The AC will consist of independent eScience and domain experts. An expert is not allowed to be part of the Assessment Committee in case a member of his/her research group submits a proposal in this call.

Appendix A:

eScience Center Core Technological Competences

The Netherlands eScience Center is the Dutch national center of excellence for the development and application of research software to advance academic research. We contribute to research projects in at least two important ways:

1. We continuously scout the international spectrum of research software; we have a broad overview of relevant software solutions and a detailed understanding of how to apply these in a broad range of research disciplines;
2. We have expertise to extend and build high-quality, sustainable, and reusable research software using modern software development techniques and standards.

Our core competence is the *creation* and *application* of research software. What software is already available? When and how can we apply this software? Can we extend already existing software? How do we build new software, if needed? In the process of extending and building software we apply high standards of software quality, and put significant effort into testing, documentation and packaging.

In addition to this core competence, we focus our efforts in three expertise areas: Optimized Data Handling, Big Data Analytics, and Efficient Computing. Together, these cover a large part of the spectrum of required software and expertise in research projects. Below each of these expertise areas is outlined further.

Optimized Data Handling

This expertise area includes a.o.:

- FAIR data
- streaming data
- databases
- linked data
- data fusion

Storing, accessing and sharing voluminous and rapidly generated data

Data are generated at increasing speed and abundance due to the miniaturization and parallelization of experiments, the deployment of sensors and the digitization of experimental practices. From radio telescopes to social media, the development and application of methods to store, access and share large volumes of rapidly generated data are becoming universally important.

At the eScience Center, we have expert knowledge on handling large volumes of data (using both traditional databases and their NoSQL alternatives), processing streaming data (as produced by sensors such as radio telescopes), and linked data (typically used to add meaning to text data). In addition, we have ample experience in sharing data according to FAIR-principles (i.e.: making data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable).

Big Data Analytics

This expertise area includes a.o.:

- machine learning
- natural language processing
- search
- computer vision
- visualization

Identifying patterns and relationships

From data to information to knowledge to insight. Current research challenges demand robust and reliable methods to identify the patterns and relationships contained in, but also obscured by, large amounts of data.

eScience approaches can enable researchers to recognize sources of relevant information, prepare raw data, use statistical tools, extract and search for meaningful information, recognize potential problems and make visualizations to communicate their findings.

With the application of statistics and state-of-the-art machine learning techniques at its core, the use of data-analytics and visualization are generic requirements for many scientists. Combining 'big data' with theory and conceptual models enables scientists to structure the wealth of data and provide skilful forecasts.

Efficient Computing

This expertise area includes a.o.:

- high-performance, distributed, and energy-aware computing
- efficient algorithms
- scalability
- ease-of-use

Optimizing for performance

As the ambition and data volumes of researchers grow, processing requirements grow accordingly. To keep up with the sizes of the data and models, software must be optimized for performance (resulting in more processing power per computer) and/or scalability (allowing more computers to share the processing load).

By applying state-of-the-art technologies such as GPUs, a significant performance increase can be achieved, while simultaneously reducing energy requirements. This requires expert knowledge, however, as GPUs are very hard to program.

Often, research data are stored in multiple locations and are too large to gather in a single place. In such cases, it may be necessary to move computing to the data, and not vice versa. Such a distributed computing solution requires specialized software to organize which computation runs where. For the user, such techniques are a means to an end, and must be made transparent to not get in the way of the research itself.

Appendix B:

The Research Software Directory (RSD)

The Research Software Directory (RSD)⁷ is the eScience Center's primary facility for open, sustainable and re-usable research software, expertise, and eScience research. First and foremost, the RSD contains *research software*. In part, this software constitutes results of the collaborations between the eScience Center and its project partners. Other parts of the RSD are formed by software that is developed in-house at the eScience Center, and by software developed by external parties to which the eScience Center has made significant contributions. The eScience Research Software Engineers contribute to the RSD by generalizing and inserting the technologies they develop in the projects in which they are partnering as a research team member.

Apart from the software itself, the RSD contains *supporting material* associated with the actual tools, applications, scientific workflows, algorithms and libraries. This material can take the form of documentation, best practice guides, tutorials, training material, papers, demos, blog posts, etcetera. This collection of supporting material grows as software is re-used in other projects. In this way, the software in the RSD is presented in its *research context*. This context helps researchers to quickly judge if a certain piece of software is relevant to their particular problem, if others in their field are using it, how to get started with the software, and whom to contact for questions. This improves the findability of software and promotes its re-use.

While the RSD is the primary facility for managing and disseminating software created in the eScience Center's project portfolio, all aspects of the RSD can be applied in a broader context than just a single project. As such, the RSD supports multiple research efforts, an entire research discipline, and even multiple disciplines. The RSD explicitly aims to promote the exchange and re-use of knowledge and best practices and to prevent fragmentation and duplication of research software.

Serving research communities

It must be stressed that the technological developments undertaken by and with the eScience Center are not aimed at realizing benefits for the eScience Center itself. All developments are in support of the scientific goals of the research project. These developments, however, are also intended to serve other research communities as much as possible, now and in the future.

⁷ See also: www.esciencecenter.nl/expertise/ and <https://www.research-software.nl/>.

Appendix C:

Software and Data Health Checks

As part of the assessment procedure of all submitted full proposals, the Netherlands eScience Center will perform *software and data health checks*. The health checks are put in place to make sure that all data and software serving as starting points of the research do not require substantial cleaning or overhaul. In case the result of either health check is negative, the eScience Center may advise its Board to not grant the proposal. More information on software and data quality can be found at:

- <https://www.openaire.eu/how-to-openly-license-research-data>
- <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles>
- <https://choosealicense.com/>
- <https://fair-software.nl>

The eScience Center expects a basic level of accessibility and quality for the data and software used in the projects it awards and collaborates in. Therefore, the research team is asked to provide the following information in the proposal:

On data (if applicable):

- A location where the data can be accessed (preferably a URL);
- The license under which the data is distributed (if any);
- Any GDPR restrictions, and if so, the policy to provide access (if any);
- A contact person for questions.

On software (if applicable):

- A location where the software can be accessed (preferably a URL to a version control system);
- The license under which the software is distributed (if any);
- A location where the documentation can be accessed (preferably a URL);
- A contact person for questions.

If the data and/or software are not available online as open data or open source, please provide the necessary information to grant access to the eScience Center for reviewing purposes. If such access cannot be granted, please contact the eScience Center to discuss alternatives.

Appendix D:

In this call, all applicants are asked to indicate the project's e-Infrastructure needs, in terms of compute hours, data storage capacity, lightpath connectivity, or otherwise. A 'use-or-explain' policy will be applied, meaning that

- projects *without* e-Infrastructure needs are asked to give a brief explanation;
- projects with clear e-Infrastructure needs are expected to select the hardware resources and services as part of the Dutch National e-Infrastructure as first option, and to indicate the expected extent of use;
- projects with clear e-Infrastructure needs that aim to use international (e.g. PRACE, EUDAT, EGI, XSEDE, etcetera) or commercial (e.g. web, cloud, etcetera) hardware and services instead are required to give a brief explanation.

The use of the Dutch National e-Infrastructure is not a requirement, nor is it a formal review criterion. However, in all cases in which the Dutch National e-Infrastructure is not used, a justification should be provided.

The Dutch National e-Infrastructure

In this call, the Dutch National e-Infrastructure is defined as follows:

all publicly-funded hardware resources (e.g. compute, data, visualization, networking, etcetera) and directly connected support services (people, software), set up and maintained with the aim to support publicly-funded research in the Netherlands, and made available to either all or a selected subset of all researchers from a.o. Dutch universities and research institutes affiliated with NWO or KNAW.

The definition distinguishes between hardware resources and services available to all researchers in the Netherlands (Category I), and those made available to a selected subset (Category II). The Category I e-Infrastructure, outlined below, is formed by the hardware resources and services provided and maintained by SURFsara, SURFnet, DANS, and – in part – also by Nikhef and RUG-CIT.

The Category II e-Infrastructure is formed by all other hardware resources and services that are accessible to a selected group of researchers following thematic or geographic criteria. Examples of such infrastructures include the Distributed ASCI Supercomputer (DAS) and the many stand-alone local facilities at various universities (e.g. the Peregrine HPC cluster (RUG-CIT), the GPFS data storage facilities (Target), the WUR HPC Cluster (Wageningen), etcetera).

Overview: Category I e-Infrastructure

While it is impossible to provide a complete overview of all resources part of the Dutch National e-Infrastructure in this call text, the following provides entrance points to the major Category I e-Infrastructure resources and services. For more information, it is advised to contact the organizations and institutes responsible for these resources directly, in particular SURF: <https://www.surf.nl/en/contact.html>.

Compute services

- Dutch National Supercomputer Cartesius
<https://www.surf.nl/en/dutch-national-supercomputer-cartesius>
- Lisa Compute Cluster: extra processing power for research
<https://www.surf.nl/en/lisa-compute-cluster-extra-processing-power-for-research>
- HPC Cloud: your flexible compute infrastructure
<https://www.surf.nl/en/hpc-cloud-your-flexible-compute-infrastructure>
- Grid: for processing and storing large data sets
<https://www.surf.nl/en/grid-for-processing-and-storing-large-data-sets>

Data storage and management

- SURFDrive: store and share your files securely in the cloud
<https://www.surf.nl/en/store-and-share-your-files-securely-in-the-cloud-with-surfdrive>
- Research Drive: securely and easily store and share research data
<https://www.surf.nl/en/research-drive-securely-and-easily-store-and-share-research-data>
- Object Store: store large quantities of data
<https://www.surf.nl/en/object-store-store-large-quantities-of-data>
- Data Archive: secure, long-term storage
<https://www.surf.nl/en/secure-long-term-storage-with-data-archive>
- Storage scale-out: expand your storage space
<https://www.surf.nl/en/expand-your-storage-space-with-storage-scale-out>
- Data Persistent Identifier: data always findable by permanent references
<https://www.surf.nl/en/data-persistent-identifier-data-always-findable-by-permanent-references>
- DataverseNL: Store, share and register research data online
<https://www.dans.knaw.nl/en/about/services/DataverseNL>
- EASY: Online archiving, depositing and downloading of research data
<https://www.dans.knaw.nl/en/about/services/easy>

Data processing and analysis

- Research Cloud
<https://www.surf.nl/en/surf-research-cloud>
- Jupyter Notebook: accessible and interactive data analysis for research
<https://www.surf.nl/en/jupyter-notebook-accessible-and-interactive-data-analysis-for-research-and-education>
- Visualisation: more insight into your data
<https://www.surf.nl/en/visualisation-more-insight-into-your-data>

SURF

For a complete overview of all Category I services provided by SURF, see:
<https://www.surf.nl/en/research-ict>

DANS

For a complete overview of all Category I services provided by DANS, see:
<http://www.dans.knaw.nl/en/about/services>